

DESCRIPTION OF SOVEREIGN SEALS ON DOCUMENTS

Dilafuz Akhmedova Khusan kizi

Faculty of Arts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the main doctoral student
of the Institute of History

+998933880186

e-mail:dilafuz.ahmedova.92@mail.ru

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ABSTRACT

In this article, information was given about the correspondence between the Bukhara Emirate, Khiva and Kokan Khanates and the seals printed on them. It was discussed that seals are the legal basis of documents. The techniques and types of making these seals were discussed. It was also shown that the seals are a historical source as examples of the practical art of medieval sealers.

Seals, which are one of the official symbols of statehood, have become important in matters of state management and ownership. Ruler's seals provided the legal basis of documents in the state administration system. He also confirmed the reliability of letters in foreign relations. Seals affixed to historical documents and their types are dealt with by the field of special historical science [5]. Seals are engraved with symbols and inscriptions on a solid body and are available in gold, silver, pewter, wax, and clay. This field of science was separated from the field of diplomacy and document studies and was formed as a special branch of science.

This discipline studies seal, insignia, and insignia molds as well as the impression or imprint on which they were made. Many researches have been carried out by the scientists of the field, and a number of scientific and methodical works have been created[9]. In the process of studying the seals of Khiva Khanate era, russian researcher A. Kun had discussed several types of seals belonging to Khiva Khans based on their internal and external features.[7]. A.A. Ivanov, who worked in the last quarter of the 20th century focused on the advantage of working with seals in his research[4]. According to N.I. Veselovsky, who directly studied the seals of the Timurid period, confirmation of the text of communication between individuals with seals increases the official importance of the document and indicates its authenticity.[2, p.229-234]. Expert scientist G.Kurbanov who directly applied to the seals of the Khanate era separately studied the seals of Bukhara emirs. The scientist emphasized that seals should be classified and studied according to their construction and structure[8,b. 240]. Sh. Ziyadov conducted a research on the seals of the Central Asian khanates and cited pictures of some seals in his work.[3].

Today, scientists who have compiled a catalog for the study of historical documents put forward different approaches to this issue. The first group of researchers emphasizes the importance of the appearance, shape, size, types of inscriptions and decorations of seals [6]. Another group of scholars puts forward an opinion about the importance of personographic, topographical and chronological signs in the documents, not the appearance of the seals[1]. Both approaches are important in studying the value of documents.

Seals, considered an important component of international correspondence, are printed at the end of letters. At the same time, next to the seal of the ruler who sent the letter, the seal of the ruler who received the letter was printed. Seals show the name and surname of the ruler, and they differ in size and shape. The series of times changed and improved their appearance. On the seals of the Khans of Turkestan, the name of the owner of the seal and the name of his father are given. The seal of the Khan, made in special workshops, was made by sealers, and even during the process of making it, the master sealer was guarded by a special guard. For example, in the Emirate of Bukhara, the seals of the head of state and officials are made of silver. The seals of other subordinates were made of copper, jade, and minerals[5, p. 210]. In the Emirate of Bukhara, the ruler's seal was kept under the control of the governor.

In the Kokan khanate, a small inok was responsible for the affairs of the cabinet. He was given a box with the ruler's seal and tasked with taking care. They also accepted applications and complaints in the name of Khan; opened the letters they brought during the reception of the ambassadors and presented them to the Khan's personal secretary (munshi)[15. b. 171].

A. Kun gave information about the seals of Khiva Khans in his article "Description of Khiva Khanate Seals".[7]. In his article, he divided seals into two types, round and star-shaped seals: decrees and blessings. He emphasized that large almond-shaped, crown-shaped seals were stamped on endowment and military documents. Most of the seals found (25 seals) are of Syed Muhammad Rahim Baha, Khan of Khiva(1865-1910), 5 of them are made of silver and the rest are made of gold. Among the seals, the most beautiful and decorated with turquoise eyes is Syed Muhammad Rahim Khan (1856-1865) informed that it is a seal belonging to

In the Middle Ages, most of the seals were made in star, leaf and almond shapes. In the process of studying the seals of the rulers of the three khanates, each seal of the khan is found in its own form. These features are as follows: The shape of the seals of the rulers of the Bukhara Emirate was round and oval. The seal of the Khans of Khiva was kept round and wrapped in a wreath. Seals of Kokan khans were mainly made in almond-shaped and almond-shaped forms with wreaths[10]. These seals applied to historical letters are typical only for international correspondence.

About 30 official documents - letters and about 10 seal prints collected in one category in the I-125 fund kept at UzMA were studied. Letters: A letter (3 pieces) sent by Bukhara emirs Nasrullah (1826-1860) and Muzaffar (1860-1885) to Khans of Khiva Rahimquli Khan (1842-45), letter (1 piece) sent to Syed Muhammad Amin Khan (1845-1855), The letters (18 pieces) sent to Muhammad Khan (1856-1865) and (2 pieces) sent to Muhammad Rahim Khan II (1865-1910) were studied. Also, the repetition of the seal of Khiva Khan Muhammad Rahim Khan II in two different forms is one of the unique aspects of the seals [11]. As a continuation of the letters, the seals of the letters sent by the Khans of Kokand Khudoyar Khan and Sultan Syed to the

Khans of Khiva Muhammad Amin Khan (1845-1855) and Syed Muhammad Khan (1856-1865) were examined.

This archive collection is under study, it can be observed that the sizes of the seals on the correspondence ranged from 2x2 cm to 3x3 cm. Despite the small size of the seals, in addition to the name and initials, the date of the seal is also written. They are embedded in a variety of bubble and embossed decorations.

The circular edges of the seals are decorated with various patterns, lines of writing are decorated with elegant flowers and varieties. In accordance with the tradition of Muslim sealology, verses of the Holy Qur'an and exemplary words are written on the outer circle of seal inscriptions. In the seals made by Khan of Khiva, in addition to his name and sharif, a short verse in Aruz weight was written: "الله ملح ال" [Al mulkillah] - (Mulk Allah's) in the center of the seal and in the circle of the seal "سرمد فضل عدل با موعيد حق نزد از احمد پاک نسل از محمد سيد سلطان" [Sultan Sayyid Muhammad az nasli pok Ahmad, Az nazdi haq muayyad, bo 'adlu fazlu sarmad] - (Sultan Sayyid Muhammad of the Ahmadi lineage (direction), ruled by God on the basis of justice) [10]. Literally, this prose sentence corresponds to the 4 repetitions in Aruz's "Ma'fulu f'ilotun" weight. The dates on the seal are 1270, 1273, 1288 AH.

One of the unique features of seals is that the inscriptions and decorations on the seal are inverted. When the seal in this condition is pressed on the sheet, the writing is right and is read correctly. For example, the name of the emir of Bukhara, Muzaffar, is printed in the following form "ریمار فظه" [17]. In addition, the date when the seal was made is also written at the junction of the name and initials. The seals of the Bukhara emir were printed between the chronological range of dates 1277-1282.[12]

The names of the ruler and his paternal grandfathers are printed on the seals of the Kokan Khans. Among the letters, there is a seal of Khudoyar Khan from the Khans of Kokan, which begins with the sentence "Ya Ahad" - "Ya Ahad" at the top of the seal. The name of Khudoyar Khan, "سید خدایار خان بن سید شیر علی محمد خان" "Syed Khudayar Khan bin Syed Sherali Muhammad Khan" is written in the central part.[13].

Among the documents, the seal of Sultan Sayyid Khan from the Khans of Koqan can be seen without difficulty even today due to its unique almond-shaped (wide) image. The ruler's name is written on the seal as "محمد سلطان سید بهادر خان" - [Muhammad Sultan Syed Bahādirkhān] - "Muhammad Sultan Syed Bahadirkhan"[14].

The following conclusions were advanced by analyzing the seals, which were part of his letters: Regardless of the historical period to which the seals belong, it helps to show the documentary system of the studied period; Seals varied in design, and the seal of the ruler's

owner was larger than that of other officials; Seals are made of various minerals and are a material source that reflects social status; Seals provide the legal basis of documents. The seals of the Central Asian khans differed geometrically in terms of design. Seals are considered to be an invaluable object as examples of the practical art of medieval sealers.

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11. OZMA. I - 125 collections, 2 - list, 220 collections, sheet 8.
12. OZMA. I - 125 collections, 2 - list, 220 collections. Sheets 1, 3, 8, 18.
13. OZMA. I - 125 collections, 2 - list, 240 collections. Sheets 1-2
14. OZMA. I - 125 collections, 2 - list, 240 collections. 3 - sheet.
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17. ريم رفظه . is the reverse shape of the seal. As a result of its writing in reverse Arabic script and in the Word program, the letters "a" and "m" - "alif" and "mim" are written together. The above-mentioned letters should not be added in the word "مفر امير" in the correct position, even in the reverse position.